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ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling
Approaches

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Omnibus Modelling to Describe the Effects of Thermisation on *Staphylococcus aureus* in Goat’s Raw Milk

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Abstract

Milk thermisation has been proposed as a strategy to improve the safety of cheeses made from unpasteurised milk as it reduces bacterial counts while preserving the organoleptic characteristics associated with raw milk cheeses. Hence, the aim of this work was to characterise the heat resistance of *S. aureus* (SA) in goat’s raw milk subjected to thermisation using omnibus modelling (simultaneous fitting of primary and secondary models). Five mL of milk were placed in sample bags and inoculated with SA (7 log CFU/mL).

The inactivation experiments were carried out in a water bath at 55, 58, 61, 62.5 and 64 °C, and the sampling was performed at appropriate times. After removing the samples from the water bath, they were immersed into an ice bath. Upon cooling, SA determination was performed. SA concentration measured at time *i* when subjected to condition *j* was estimated as:

$$Y_{ij} = Y_{0j} - \left(\frac{t}{\chi_j}\right)^{\beta_j} + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad Y_{0j} = Y_{0\text{mean}} + u_j$$

$$\sqrt{\chi_j} = a_1 + a_2 * \text{Temperature} + a_3 * \text{Temperature}^2 + v_j$$

$$\sqrt{\beta_j} = b_1 + b_2 * \text{Temperature} + b_3 * \text{Temperature}^2$$

The omnibus approach allowed to described well all the inactivation curves and estimate SA inactivation parameters in heat-treated milk. The positive intercepts a_1 (343.6±14.87) and b_1 (74.32±9.293) allude to the concavity of the fitting and the quadratic effect of temperature on $\sqrt{\chi}$ and $\sqrt{\beta}$. The negative linear effects of temperature on $\sqrt{\chi}$ and $\sqrt{\beta}$ ($a_2 = -10.87$; $b_2 = -2.427$) were anticipated since higher temperatures should lead to shorter inactivation times. The correlation coefficient between a_1 and b_1 was 0.779.

Validation of the model at 58 °C, 61 °C and 62.5 °C by the “leave-one-out method” was successfully performed, demonstrating its aptitude to be used in the design of lethality treatments to achieve specific reductions of SA in goats’ raw milk, thus contributing to the enhancement of the microbiological quality and safety of raw milk cheeses.

Keywords: Weibull; cheesemaking; milk treatment.

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